

USE OF DIDACTIC MATERIALS IN LEARNING WORD CLASSES'S IN PRIMARY GRADES.

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ABSTRACT

*In this article, several important aspects of teaching
vocabulary in elementary mother tongue classes are
analyzed. Also, comments were made about the
characteristics of didactic materials used for teaching
vocabulary in primary classes.*

In modern pedagogy, didactics is considered as a separate field dealing with the theory of education and enlightenment. Determining the content of education, discovering the laws of the educational process, and finding the most effective methods and ways of teaching are the main problems of didactics. Didactic materials are tools designed for acquiring knowledge, forming and strengthening skills and competencies in the educational process. They help to make the educational process effective and interesting. Didactic materials attract students' attention, visually explain knowledge and create an opportunity for independent work.

Vocabulary teaching in primary grades is important in the formation of students' knowledge of the mother tongue. This process creates the basis for the correct understanding of the native language, the clear and logical expression of thoughts, as well as the development of writing and speaking.

The important aspects of teaching word groups in primary mother tongue classes are:

- phrases are the main stage of mastering grammatical norms, and this knowledge will play a key role in learning more complex topics in the future, including sentence analysis and writing rules. Pupils, knowing what categories words belong to, better understand their function;
- having knowledge about word groups teaches students to make correct sentences, to express their thoughts logically and clearly. For example, the correct use of nouns, verbs, adjectives and other word groups helps to make the speech rich and meaningful;
- Primary school students will not have mastered the language yet. Teaching vocabulary increases their vocabulary, develops the ability to analyze texts and choose the right words in written works;

- children learn to analyze the meaning, form and function of words to differentiate word groups. This is important in developing their logical thinking skills;

- by understanding the structure of the language and its rules, children develop a sense of respect for their mother tongue. Knowledge of vocabulary helps them understand and master the literary language;

- learning vocabulary in primary grades helps in mastering not only linguistics, but also other subjects. Correctly structured sentences and logical explanations help to correctly understand and answer questions in mathematics, science and other sciences;

- when students start learning a foreign language, it is important for them to know about vocabulary in advance. Because this knowledge makes it easier to understand the grammatical rules of other languages;

Useful features of didactic materials: simplify the learning process; facilitates the explanation of complex topics; makes students interested in the lesson; an interactive approach attracts their attention; increases practical skills; helps master the subject not only theoretically, but also practically. For example,

- show types, signs and examples of word groups using colorful and understandable posters;

- cards written in a different color for each group of words teach students to separate words correctly;

- attracting students' attention by using electronic presentations or short animations during the lesson;

- "Who is faster?": organization of competitions to divide the words written on the screen or blackboard into word groups;

- developing students' creativity by performing in the role determined for each word group;

- placing sheets with different words in the classroom and asking students to place them in the necessary word groups;

- give students short texts and assign them as a task to divide the words into word groups;

- choosing words from the texts, defining their category, and then explaining the role of these words in the sentence;

- creative and interesting processing of exercises presented in existing textbooks;

- additional questions for each topic, for example, "What signs should be paid attention to when distinguishing word groups?" include questions like;

- testing and strengthening students' knowledge using interactive programs for learning vocabulary;

- mastering the subject by watching interesting video lessons.

The use of didactic materials in learning vocabulary significantly increases organization in the educational process. Such materials help students master theoretical knowledge and help them apply it in practice. This process helps to increase students' interest in the lesson, ensure their active participation and retain knowledge for a long time. Didactic materials allow students to make the subject visible and understandable. The learning process with the help of pictures, flashcards, tables and games engages multi-sensory systems (sight, hearing, movement), which helps students to

master the subject more deeply. In addition, with the help of didactic materials, the teacher will have the opportunity to combine different educational methods, taking into account the age characteristics and individual needs of students. Some learners learn best with visual materials, while others prefer auditory or hands-on learning. through didactic materials, elementary school students develop not only working with word groups, but also various creative and critical thinking skills. For example, students' logical thinking skills are developed by separating word groups, using them correctly, and playing games related to them.

In short, didactic materials are an integral part of the process of learning vocabulary, which make the learning process of elementary school students more effective. The use of such materials increases the motivation of elementary school students, ensures participation at every stage of learning the mother tongue. Organization of each lesson process in an interesting and purposeful way, encouraging students to be active, increases the enthusiasm of primary school students for learning.

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